

Water-tightness Airborne Detection Implementation

D7.2. LCC Report

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Executive Summary

The objective of the present LCC study is to perform a complementary evaluation to the LCA performed in D7.1 but from an economic perspective. To do this, an environmental LCC approach has been applied. This methodology comprises the following kind of costs:

- Investment costs (acquisition costs)
- Operation costs
- Maintenance costs
- End-of-life costs
- Externalities costs (environmental costs)

The representativeness and accuracy of this study directly depends on the quantity and quality of the information provided by the involved partners. In order to establish a LCC study as much realistic as possible, most of the partners were asked for data to perform this deliverable depending on their profile: costs of acquiring the equipment (AM, GG, ONERA, NTGS), operation costs (AM, ONERA) and market estimations and detection efficiency (SGL, SST). Besides, some costs that were difficult to estimate, such as the end of life costs, were taken from specialized literature.

The content of this deliverable is divided into two main sections. In the first one, the LCC study itself is presented, differentiating between the costs associated with each of the techniques developed in the project: MAV and UAV. In the second part of this report, a simplified economic evaluation has been performed, considering not only the costs involved in the LCC study but also the incomes that could be obtained for a company running the WADI water leakage detection systems. In those studies, the expected annual profits and cash flows have been also estimated to evaluate the profitability of the investment by using some economic parameters such as the payback period, the NPV or the IRR.

In summary, LCC results indicate that the most significant costs are those related to the operation activities (up to 82% of the total LCC for MAV and 97% for UAV). Most specifically, processing the information recorded during the flights is the costliest factor both for the MAV and UAV units. Regarding the investment costs, the plane acquisition cost (aircraft) is much greater than the cost of acquiring the remaining components of the MAV unit, whereas the purchase of the batteries is the main acquisition cost that must be afforded during the life cycle of the UAV unit. Finally, the maintenance, end-of-life and environmental costs are significantly smaller in comparison to the rest of the cost categories.

Regarding the economic study, the profitability of both systems is clear. The payback period of the MAV system would be around 3 years with a service demand of 400 h/year, and the UAV unit payback would be lower than 1 year with an estimated demand of the service of 600 h/year.

The results and conclusions obtained in this deliverable represent a first step to evaluate the economic feasibility of the developed technologies. However, some of the considerations taken to perform this deliverable could change after performing a deeper market analysis and business plan (WP9) and then, results should be updated.

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2 Introduction

Water is a valuable resource, critical to economic development. Lots of countries worldwide are currently facing challenges in water management. Moreover, not all the transported water reaches the customer, but a significant portion of it is lost due to leakage from water distribution networks.

WADI project aims to save water losses in non-urban areas. Agriculture is the economic activity with the highest consumption of water in the EU. On average, 44% of water abstraction in Europe is used for agriculture, and Southern Europe even uses larger percentages [1]. Moreover, water leaks generate different damages as the following ones [2]:

- Water losses generate an economic impact. As described in deliverable 9.1, the marginal cost of water is about 0.2 €/m³, and a leak of only one litre per minute can cause a water loss of 525 m³ in a year. Also, water leaks significantly increase operating costs, especially costs associated with the electricity consumption of water supply pumps [3].
- Losses from water supply systems force water agencies to extract more water from freshwater sources, which puts more stress on this type of ecosystems or to restrict water supply, representing a direct impact in their annual incomes.
- Undetected leaks contribute to pipe failures.
- Leaks in water pipes may allow contaminant to enter in the water systems, causing a reduction of water quality.
- Water supply generates several environmental impacts, e.g. electricity consumption for water extraction and distribution or water depletion.
- An inefficient water distribution system erodes utility revenue [4].
- Leakage has a negative impact on the objectives of the Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) [5].
- Water losses reduce the reliability of the water supply network. As a consequence, this fact could lead farmers to find alternative sources, even more expensive, to protect themselves from the risks of unreliable water supplies.

By these reasons, it is important to reach efficient water leaks detection and control systems. WADI project proposes an airborne leak detection surveillance service out of urban areas. Its innovative concept consists in coupling and optimising off-the-shelf optical remote sensing devices (multispectral and infrared cameras) and applying them on two complementary aerial platforms: manned and unmanned. One of the main advantages of WADI service is that it can also monitor rough areas with difficult access and geographical conditions with a significantly lower price.

According to some predictions made during first stages of the project development, if WADI's technology were applied in the 20% of the European water network, it could reach the next savings per year:

- 1.27 billion m³ of water savings.
- 815 million kWh of energy savings.
- 464.55 million avoided CO₂ kg.

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However, the previous estimations have been revised and recalculated in WP7 in order to quantify the real impact caused by the application of the WADI innovative technology. Firstly, environmental impacts have been calculated by applying a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to the WADI water leaks detection systems (D7.1). Secondly, from the results obtained in D7.1, Life Cycle Costing (LCC) has been calculated in the current deliverable, within the task 7.1 activities. Both LCA and LCC studies are based on the life cycle perspective, taking into account all the stages involved from the extraction and processing of the raw materials to the consideration of different end-of life treatments, after the end of the use stage. Finally, results from D7.1 and D7.2 will be used as inputs in the remaining WP7 tasks, as well as in some tasks of WP9.

3 LCC methodology

Life-Cycle Costing (LCC) is a magnitude that evaluates the costs of an asset throughout its life cycle. Owners, users and managers need to make decisions on the acquisition and ongoing use of many different assets including items of equipment and the facilities to house them. The initial capital outlay cost is usually clearly defined and is often a key factor influencing the choice of asset given a number of alternatives from which to select. However, the initial capital outlay cost is only a portion of the costs over an asset's life cycle that needs to be considered in making the right choice for asset investment. The total cost of ownership of an asset is often far greater than the initial capital outlay cost and can vary significantly between different alternative solutions to a given operational need.

Thus, the LCC technique in procurement aims to determine the cost of ownership of a fixed asset (purchase price, installation, operation, maintenance and upgrading, disposal, and other costs) during the asset's economic life.

The conventional LCC techniques most widely used by companies and/or governments are based on a purely financial valuation. Here, four main cost categories are assessed [6]:

- **Investment costs:** This category includes the purchase price and, when applicable, the associated costs, such as installation, commissioning, and initial training of users.
- **Operating costs:** This category includes consumption of energy, consumables, raw materials and other materials needed for the use of the product.
- **Maintenance costs:** This category includes any service charges in this respect (cleaning tasks, for example) and spare parts that have to be periodically replaced.
- **End-of-life costs:** such as decommissioning and disposal.

On the other hand, there is also an environmental approach of this analysis. Environmental LCC (ELCC) methodology takes into account not only the four above-mentioned main cost categories, but also **external environmental costs**. For this purpose, it is required to consider the impacts obtained from a previous LCA and then, to translate those values into economic values through weighting tools. In this manner, the LCC analysis covers all the costs incurred by the extended waste management system [7]. This approach is required in Europe for SPP (Sustainable Public Procurement) as specified in 2014/24/EU Art. 68.

This weighting procedure to convert the environmental impacts on economic value is carried out through environmental externalities according to specialized references [8]–[10]. The procedure to evaluate the environmental costs of a product or service is summarized in Figure 1.

The Life Cycle Costing can be as simple as the elaboration of a table or inventory including the future expected costs or can be a complex model from where to generate scenarios based on assumptions about future cost drivers. Generally, the second data treatment provides more accurate results but the process is much more complicated. The kind of analysis performed in each case will depend on the kind of asset assessed, the ability to predict future costs and the significance of the future costs to the decision being made by the organization.

Figure 1. Structure of the LCC methodologies

In the current analysis, the accuracy of every analysis depends on the amount of data provided by each partner and its quality. These considerations are described during the analysis performed along this deliverable.

3.1 LCC methodology Within WADI Project

Within WADI project, the LCC methodology has been applied to assess the MAV and UAV units. In addition to the traditional parameters that are normally considered to calculate the LCC of a product (investment, operation, maintenance and end-of-life costs), other economic metrics have been used to assess the profitability and economic viability of the investments needed to offer the WADI water leaks detection methods. Concretely, Table 1 shows the list of economic indicators that have been evaluated in this deliverable.

Table 1. Economic impact categories included in LCC WADI methodology.

Indicator	Unit
Externalities (environmental cost)	€
Life cycle cost (LCC)	€
Net Present Value (NPV) of investments	€
Internal Rate of Return on investments (IRR)	%
Return of investment (payback)	years

Besides the parameters considered within the LCC methodologies, the following economic parameters have been calculated:

- Net Present Value (NPV) of the investment. It is the aggregation of cash flows along an exploitation period, or the asset lifetime, including the initial investment according to a discount rate. For this analysis, taking an average inflation rate expectancy to deduce the annual value loss of the currency is proposed.
- Internal Return Rate (IRR). It is the annual yield of the investment, expressed as a percentage of the initial investment. To ensure the profitability, this value must

exceed the average inflation rate, and the financing interest rate. The Internal Return Rate is the discount rate that makes $NPV = 0$. In other words, this is the annual return rate of an investment.

- Payback time. It is the time, in years, that it is needed to return the initial investment needed for the acquisition of all the equipment of the WADI units.

4 LCC assessment

4.1 Manned aircraft LCC

As explained before, four kind of categories are used to quantify all the costs considered in the development of a Life Cycle Cost study: acquisition, maintenance, operation and end-of-life, as well as one additional category which englobes the externalities cost caused by the environmental impacts. In the following sections, a detailed description of each category is included for the study of the Manned Vehicle Aircraft (MAV).

4.1.1 Acquisition costs

The first category includes all the required costs to acquire all the equipment necessary to perform the flights with the MAV technology developed within the WADI project. On the one hand, Table 2 contains the absolute cost of each component. All those costs will have to be afforded the first year of operation. On the other hand, in order to allocate the acquisition cost of each component to one hour of effective flight, the lifetime of the components have been estimated. This assigned hourly cost is also included in the table below.

Table 2. Acquisition costs of the WADI manned aircraft

Investment costs (Acquisition)	
Aircraft support and integration platform (NTGS)	
Cost	18000 €
Lifetime (expected)	20 years
Time of effective use	1325 h/year
Allocation per h of flight	0.7 €/h
Aircraft manufacturing (Air Marine)	
Cost	517620 €
Lifetime (expected)	30 years
Time of effective use	400 h/year
Allocation per h of flight	43 €/h
Aircraft cameras (Onera)	
Inertial Measurement Unit: Spatial dual. EK – Advanced Navigation	
Cost	9045 €
Lifetime (expected)	6 years
Time of effective use	400 h/year
Allocation per h of flight	3.77 €/h
Multispectral camera: Spectrocam-VIS camera 1.4 MP – ACAL bfi	

Cost	24120 €
Lifetime (expected)	6 years
Time of effective use	400 h/year
Allocation per h of flight	10.05 €/h

IR camera: NOXCAM 640L - NOXANT

Cost	113232 €
Lifetime (expected)	8500 h/lifetime
Allocation per h of flight	13.32 €/h

Console	
Cost	60000 €
Modification	40000 €
Lifetime (expected)	15 years
Time of effective use	400 h/year
Allocation per h of flight	16.66 €/h

Graphically, the investment costs distribution is depicted in Figure 2. The graph on the left shows the distribution of the absolute acquisition cost of one unit of each component, without taking into account that some components must be replaced along the lifetime of the system. On the other hand, the graph on the right has been made considering the cost of each component assigned to one hour of MAV flight. This way, the longer the lifetime of a component, the smaller the cost allocated to each hour of use.

In absolute cost terms, the aircraft (plane) is the component with the greatest cost. The difference with the rest of the components of the MAV unit is so big that while the plane cost is 70 % of the total initial investment cost, the cost of the second more expensive component, which is the IR camera, only is the 15 % of the total cost. If the relative investments costs are considered, now the contribution of the plane cost decreases to 49 %. The reason of this reduction is that the plane has longer lifetime than most of the other components (30 years) and therefore, they should be periodically replaced if the WADI service wants to be offered during a long period of time. On the other side of the spectrum, the console has a low contribution over the absolute cost at the moment of acquiring the MAV unit but due to its shorter lifetime (8,500 h), it is responsible for 19 % of the total hourly depreciation costs.

The previous results are a good example about why is so important to evaluate the life cycle costs of an asset before making a purchase and to compare the life cycle costs of several alternatives, since not always the lowest investment costs at the moment of the purchase are related to the lowest costs during its life cycle.

Figure 2. a) absolute and b) relative investment cost distribution of the MAV system

4.1.2 Operation cost

The operation costs considered in this section are those incurred during the use stage of the manned aircraft. The most relevant operation cost is due to the fuel consumed during the flights. This cost strongly varies depending on the country where the fuel price is taken. Other costs with important variation per country are those associated with labour costs or salaries of the people directly working in the flights or in the information processing. Besides, there are costs that can significantly change not only when different countries are compared but also different regions or areas. They are, for example, the costs of permissions needed to flight in a specific area.

As an example, Table 3 contains the operation costs estimated by Air Marine if the MAV WADI service were offered in France.

Table 3. Operation costs of the WADI manned aircraft

Flights information - Operation costs (Air Marine)			
Fuel	Type of fuel	AVGAS 100LL	
	Consumption	40	l/h
	Fuel price	2	€/l
	Hourly cost	80	€/h of flight
Direct labour costs		60	€/h of flight
Flying permissions	Cost	14	€/h of flight
Data processing cost	Labour costs	60	€/h
	Processing time	12	h/flight
	Hourly cost	720	€/h of flight

4.1.3 Maintenance costs

The average maintenance costs of a small aircraft, per hour of flight, are collected in Table 4.

Table 4. Maintenance costs of the WADI manned aircraft

Maintenance costs (Air Marine)	
Average maintenance costs	136 €/h of flight

The mentioned maintenance cost is the proportional allocation of the cost incurred every time that a revision is done to an aircraft depending on the periodicity that those revisions needs to be performed. According to Air Marine, three kinds of revisions are periodically performed:

- A short maintenance revision every 50 hours of flight.
- A long maintenance revision every 100 hours (it includes 50h visit).
- A very long maintenance revision every 200 hours (it includes 50h and 100h visits).

4.1.4 End-of-life costs

Regarding the end-of-life strategies, a detailed explanation of the procedures normally applied to manage this equipment after finishing its use stage can be found in D7.1.

A goal of the disposal or retirement phase, as it is often called, is the reduction of environmental waste. This is regulated in the European Union by the 'originator principle' which states: "he who inflicts harm on the environment has to pay for cleaning the damage on the environment". At the end of a products life, the product can be recycled, re-manufactured, reused or disposed. Since a product can never be completely recycled, one wants to maximize the recycled resources while minimizing the effort to accomplish this [11].

Disposal cost model consists of the following contributors: disassembly labour, disposal of non-reusable material, sale of scrap material and resale value of on-board equipment. This cost could be negative if the aircraft were sold intact at the end of its useful life. However, the resale of systems, such as the engines and avionics, is thought to be unlikely, because technology in these areas changes very quickly. For this reason, the value of these items has been neglected [12].

Some components such as the main platform structure may be reused in other similar projects. However, brushless motors, on-board computer and motor controller board should be recycled at authorized recycling plants. Regarding the aircraft, some parts will be recycled, although many components will be thrown away to landfill.

It is not easy to find LCC studies of aircrafts where the disposal costs are considered. Many studies consider that the contribution of the end-of-life costs is so small if compared with the other costs incurred in the aircraft life cycle that can be neglected without committing an appreciable error [11], [13].

For performing the current study, it was considered the information published by Woodford [12], where different aircrafts are analyzed from a LCC perspective. In all the cases included in his study, the disposal costs represent around 0.5 % of the total life cycle cost, so that is the value taken for this study.

With all the above, the disposal cost of the WADI manned solution is considered to be **2.20 €/h of flight**.

4.1.5 Externalities cost

For the calculation of the externalities cost, the environmental impacts caused by the MAV unit (deliverable 7.1: LCA; Table 5-2) have been converted into euros by using some monetization factors taken from scientific publications found in literature [14], [15]. As the cited publications contains monetization factors based on prices from 2014-2015 (depending on the source), inflation rates have been considered to update those factors to year 2019. Table 5 contains the externalities cost caused by the MAV water leaks detection method during its complete life cycle.

Table 5. Externalities cost of the MAV unit, in €. Results calculated from the impacts obtained in the LCA study (D7.1)

Externalities cost, €	
Climate change	16008.8
Ozone depletion	4.6
Terrestrial acidification	37038.5
Freshwater eutrophication	55.6
Marine eutrophication	122.8
Human toxicity	9551.0
Photochemical oxidant formation	3618.6
Particulate matter formation	9933.8
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	195.3
Freshwater ecotoxicity	6.1
Marine ecotoxicity	1.8
Ionising radiation	139.0
Agricultural land occupation	792.4
Urban land occupation	162.1
Natural land transformation	0.0
Water depletion	21347.7
Metal depletion	0.0
Fossil depletion	2998.1
TOTAL EXTERNALITIES COST	101985.9 €

Lifetime: 30 years; 400 h/year

Externalities cost per hour of flight [€/h]	8.5 €
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The total cost of the externalities associated with the MAV technique is 101985 €. This cost includes the monetization of all the impacts caused during the manufacturing of the plane, the cameras and other components, as well as the impacts generated during water leakage inspection due to the gasoline consumption of the plane. In order to allocate the externality cost to each hour of flight, it was considered that the lifespan of the MAV unit is 30 years and each year, the effective flight hours are 400. Under this assumption, the externalities cost attributable to each hour of flight is **8.5 €**.

The relative distribution of the most relevant environmental categories is depicted in Figure 3. To prepare that graph, all the impact indicators with a contribution greater than 1 % of the total externality cost have been included. As a first conclusion, it can be seen that about 37 % of the total cost is generated due to the impacts associated with terrestrial acidification. Besides, the effects of the water depletion and climate change categories are also significant over the total cost, being responsible for 21 % and 16 % respectively of the total environmental cost.

Figure 3. Relative distribution of externalities cost (MAV) according to the environmental category where it has been generated

In order to identify the origin of the costs, these two latter indicators, climate change and water depletion, have been selected to a deeper study. To do this, Figure 4 represents the externality cost formation caused by the greenhouse gases emissions and the water consumed along the life cycle chain of the MAV unit. In both cases, the gasoline consumption and the manufacture of the plane (MAV TECNAM) are the main contributors. In the climate change cost formation, the contribution of the gasoline consumption is especially remarkable, since it causes more than 90 % of the total impact. On the other hand, the cost caused by the water depletion indicator is more balanced between the plane manufacturing and the gasoline consumption. In both cases, the contribution of the remaining MAV components is negligible in comparison.

Figure 4. Externalities cost formation because of the impacts incurred over the climate change and the water depletion indicators. MAV unit.

4.2 Unmanned aircraft LCC

4.2.1 Acquisition costs

The acquisition cost of the drone, as well as the cost of its cameras and sensors, was provided by Galileo Geosystems. For each component of the UAV unit, the number of hours that could normally work has been estimated (lifespan). To distribute the investment cost of each component among its effective hours of use, a linear depreciation method has been applied. However, since there are many factors affecting the number of hours that every component could be used along its lifetime, other allocation criteria could also be applied if properly justified.

Table 6. Acquisition costs of the WADI unmanned aircraft

Investment costs (Acquisition)		
UAV drones manufacturing (Galileo Geosystems)		
Drone general structure		
Cost	2500	€
Lifetime (expected)	5	years
Time of effective use	600	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	0.83	€/h
Drone batteries		
Cost of each battery	300	€
Lifetime (expected)	2	years
Time of effective use	64	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	2.34	€/h
Drone remote control		

Cost	2000	€
Lifetime (expected)	10	years
Time of effective use	600	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	0.33	€/h

Drone others

Cost	1000	€
Lifetime (expected)	3	years
Time of effective use	600	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	0.55	€/h

UAV drones' cameras and sensors (Galileo Geosystems)**Multispectral camera: Micasense RedEdge**

Cost	4500	€
Lifetime (expected)	10	years
Time of effective use	600	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	0.75	€/h

IR camera: FLIR Vue Pro-R

Cost	3500	€
Lifetime (expected)	10	years
Time of effective use	600	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	0.58	€/h

Software (Galileo Geosystems)

Cost	6000	€/licence
Lifetime (expected)	10	years
Time of effective use	600	h/year
Allocation per h of flight	1.00	€/h

The investment costs distribution is graphically depicted in Figure 5. The absolute investment costs refer to the total cost of acquiring one unit of drone system, without taking into account that some components must be replaced along the lifetime of the system. On the other hand, when the relative costs are graphed, it was considered the cost of each component assigned to one hour of drone flight.

The durability of each component can vary depending on its effective use and the way it is used. For this reason, it was agreed by CIRCE and GG to define a life cycle scenario considering the average lifetime of each component under the following work routine:

- Every day, the effective flight time with the drone is 2.5 hours. This value was estimated considering that, in a workday, the person driving the drone needs to go

to the area with potential water leaks and change several times its position in order to explore a wide section of pipelines.

- The flights can be done 20 days/month and 12 months/year (600 h/year). This scenario is quite optimistic because it considers that the innovative technology would have enough demand to operate during the whole year at full capacity.
- Every flight has a duration of 16 minutes (this is the duration of a battery). If the drone flights 2.5 hours every day, between 9 and 10 batteries must be consumed (and recharged) per working day.
- Every battery is used 16 min/day. In two years, its effective use is $0.26\text{h/day} * 20\text{days/month} * 12\text{months/year} = 64\text{h/year}$.
- For this study, the lifetime of a drone was considered 5 years. The lifetime of a battery is about 2 years and then, it must be replaced. In 5 years, batteries must be replaced 2.5 times (total equivalent batteries required in 5 years are about 23 batteries).
- During the lifetime of the drone (5 years), the engine and the propellers must be replaced at least one time. For this reason, it was considered that the lifetime of these components is 2.5 years.

Considering the assumptions mentioned in the previous list, the lifetime used for each component of the UAV system can be found in Table 7. The lifetime of the general structure of the drone was considered as reference unit; this is, 5 years. The table below also contains the equivalent units of each component that are “consumed” in 5 years.

Table 7. Lifetime of the most relevant components of the UAV

Component	Lifetime [years]	Equivalent units in 5 years
Drone (general structure)	5	Reference unit
Multispectral camera	10	0.5
IR camera	10	0.5
Propeller	2.5	2
Engine	2.5	2
Batteries	2	23

In absolute terms, the costliest components are the software licence (30%), multispectral camera (23%), and IR camera (18%). However, the lifetime of these components is greater than the lifetime of the drone components. Therefore, when the relative costs study is performed, the drone components are the elements with the highest costs. For example, the drone batteries have a weight of 37% in the hourly cost distribution (average number of batteries used in one day: 9.3 batteries), as well as the drone general structure, whose contribution in the hourly cost is 13%. The sum of the three components previously mentioned as the most relevant costs in the absolute cost evaluation is only slightly greater than the 37% of the total relative cost. This is the reason why is so important to perform a life cycle cost evaluation, because not always the greatest costs incurred at the moment of an asset acquisition are the greatest expenses from a life cycle perspective.

Figure 5. a) Absolute and b) relative investment costs distribution of the drone system (UAV).

4.2.2 Operation costs

The second cost category includes all the operation costs that take place when the UAV unit is used. For this reason, and unlike the investment costs, operation costs are directly proportional to the number of flights performed.

Table 8. Operation costs of the WADI unmanned aircraft

Flights information - Operation costs (Galileo Geosystems)			
Inspection Costs	Flying permissions	0.25	€/h
	Costs of visual oversight	7	€/flight
		26.25	€/h
Batteries cost	Recharging cost	0.05	€/flight
	Autonomy	16	min/flight
		0.18	€/h
Direct labour costs	Cost per hour	40	€/h
	Cost of flying (16min/flight)	40	€/h
		53.33	€/h
Data processing cost	Labour costs	40	€/h_processing
	Processing time	1.5	h/flight
		60	€/flight
			225
Digital maps cost		0	€/h

Other costs	Other costs	10	€/flight
		37.5	€/h

4.2.3 Maintenance costs

Approximate values of maintenance costs that are normally incurred in one year were provided by Galileo Geosystems. To allocate those maintenance costs to each hour of flight, the total annual costs were added and divided among the number of hours that the drone is estimated to be working in a year. The results obtained can be found in Table 9.

Table 9. Maintenance costs of the WADI unmanned aircraft

Maintenance costs (Galileo Geosystems)	
Maintenance cost	800 €/year
Other consumables costs	1800 €/year
Insurance costs	300 €/year
Time of effective use	600 h/year
Total allocation per h of flight	4.8 €/h

4.2.4 End-of-life costs

A detailed explanation about the end-of-life scenarios for the UAV unit can be found in D7.1. In the current deliverable, those scenarios are quantified from an economic point of view. According to the information received from Galileo Geosystems, the following disposal treatments are normally applied to each component:

- Drone general structure: Landfill.
- Drone batteries: Battery dump.
- Drone remote control: Landfill.
- Multispectral camera: Managing as electronic waste.
- IR camera. Managing as electronic waste.

There is a lack of studies related to the calculation of life cycle costs of drones or unmanned aircrafts. In order to take a representative value for this study, it was taken the assumption made by Erdman and Mitchum [16], who established that the disposal cost of a drone is about 10 % of its acquisition costs. In this case, the disposal cost of the unmanned WADI solution is considered to be **0.15 €/flight**.

4.2.5 Externalities cost

In order to calculate the externalities costs for the UAV unit, the same procedure as for the MAV unit externalities cost has been followed. Environmental impacts included in Table 5.4 of deliverable 7.1 have been converted into economic units by using the monetization factors estimated in [14] and [15]. Since the electricity consumption of recharging the batteries is responsible for most of the environmental impact caused during the life cycle of

the UAV unit, two scenarios have been differentiated, taken into account that the electricity were generated with the electricity mix of Portugal or with the electricity mix of France.

Table 10. Externalities cost of the UAV unit, in €. Results calculated from the impacts obtained in the LCA study (D7.1)

Externalities cost		
	Electricity mix: France	Electricity mix: Portugal
Climate change	18.9	32.3
Ozone depletion	0.0	0.0
Terrestrial acidification	110.2	153.4
Freshwater eutrophication	1.9	2.1
Marine eutrophication	0.8	1.0
Human toxicity	131.5	130.3
Photochemical oxidant formation	3.6	5.1
Particulate matter formation	34.3	43.9
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1.4	1.3
Freshwater ecotoxicity	0.0	0.0
Marine ecotoxicity	0.1	0.1
Ionising radiation	0.8	0.1
Agricultural land occupation	5.8	4.2
Urban land occupation	3.9	5.6
Natural land transformation	0.0	0.0
Water depletion	275.2	508.1
Metal depletion	0.0	0.0
Fossil depletion	0.6	0.9
TOTAL EXTERNALITIES COST	588.8	888.4

Lifetime: 5 years; 600 h/year

Externalities cost per hour of flight [€/h]	0.2	0.3
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The externalities cost generated due to the environmental impacts of the UAV unit during its whole lifetime is 589 € if the French electricity mix is considered, and 889 € if the electricity is assumed to be generated in Portugal. In order to allocate the total cost among each hour of effective flight, it was considered that the lifespan of the UAV unit is 5 years and its annual effective use is 600 h/year. This way, unit environmental costs of 0.2 €/h and 0.3 €/h have been obtained. Even though these costs are not part of the accounting balance of the company which will perform the water leaks detection flights, since they do not represent a cost for the company but for the society, they must be considered under the environmental LCC approach.

In relative terms, the impact categories with a weight higher than 1% over the total externalities cost have been graphed in Figure 6. Both in the French and Portuguese scenario, the greatest contributor is the cost associated with the water depletion indicator (48% and 58% respectively). Besides, it is also significant the externality cost caused by the terrestrial acidification and human toxicity impacts (between 15 and 23%). The monetized impact of the remaining environmental indicators is small in comparison.

Figure 6. Relative distribution of externalities cost (UAV) according to the environmental category where it has been generated.

Finally, in order to evaluate which consumptions incurred along the life cycle of the UAV unit generate the externalities cost, the relative distribution of the externalities cost formation caused by the climate change and water depletion indicators have been plotted in Figure 7 for the Portuguese case. In both indicators, the externality cost is mainly caused by the electricity consumed to recharge the batteries, being this consumption even responsible for more than 75 % of the total water depletion externality. Besides, in these impact categories, the externality cost caused by the drone batteries is also quite significant (42 % of the total climate change externality).

Figure 7. Externalities cost formation because of the impacts incurred over the climate change and water depletion indicators. Portuguese electricity mix.

4.3 Summary of life cycle costs

To sum up the results obtained in the previous section, Table 11 contains all the life cycle costs associated with the MAV unit per hour of effective flight, and Table 12 and Table 13 contain a summary of the costs for the UAV unit, taking as reference unit one flight of 16 minutes and one hour of effective flight respectively.

Table 11. Summary of life cycle costs incurred for the WADI manned aircraft. Units: € per hour of flight.

Investment Costs	€/h	88 €/h of flight
Aircraft	43.1	
Platform	0.7	
Inertial Measurement Unit	3.8	
Multispectral camera	10.0	
IR camera	13.3	
Console	16.7	
Operation Costs		1028 €/h of flight
Labour costs	60	
Fuel	80	
Flying permissions	14	
Data processing costs	720	
Displacement costs	154	
Maintenance Costs		136 €/h of flight
End-of-life Costs		2.2 €/h of flight
TOTAL Life Cycle Cost		1254 €/h of flight
Externalities cost	8.5	
TOTAL Environmental Life Cycle Cost		1262 €/h of flight

Regarding the MAV unit, Figure 8 contains the life cycle costs distribution according to its nature per hour of real flight. More than 80 % of the total cost is due to operational costs, mainly labour costs associated with data processing. There are also other costs with significant participation in the total LCC such as the maintenance costs (11 %) and the initial investment costs (7 %). A detailed description of each one, as well as the components included in each cost category can be found in the previous section 4.1.

Figure 8. Cost distribution per hour of flight. MAV unit.

The summary of the costs related to the UAV unit are collected in Table 12 and Table 13.

Table 12. Summary of life cycle costs incurred for the WADI unmanned aircraft (drone). Units per flight, 16 min

Investment Costs	€/flight	1.7 €/flight
Drone general structure	0.2	
Drone batteries	0.6	
Drone remote control	0.1	
Drone others	0.1	
Multispectral camera: Micasense RedEdge	0.2	
IR camera: FLIR Vue Pro-R	0.2	
Software	0.3	
Operation Costs		102.0 €/flight
Labour costs (driving the drone)	24.9	
Batteries recharging	0.04	
Flying permissions	0.06	
Visual oversight	7.0	
Data processing costs	60.0	
Other fixed costs	10.0	
Maintenance Costs		1.3 €/flight
End-of-life Costs		0.17 €/flight
TOTAL Life Cycle Cost		105.2 €/flight
Externalities cost	0.08	
TOTAL Environmental Life Cycle Cost		105.2 €/flight

Table 13. Summary of life cycle costs incurred for the WADI unmanned aircraft (drone). Units per hour of effective flight

Investment Costs	€/h	6.4	€/h of flight
Drone general structure	0.8		
Drone batteries	2.3		
Drone remote control	0.33		
Drone others	0.56		
Multispectral camera: Micasense RedEdge	0.75		
IR camera: FLIR Vue Pro-R	0.58		
Software	1.00		
Operation Costs		382.5	€/h of flight
Labour costs (driving/preparing the drone)	93.3		
Batteries recharging	0.18		
Flying permissions	0.25		
Visual oversight	26.25		
Data processing costs	225		
Other fixed costs	37.5		
Maintenance Costs		4.8	€/h of flight
End-of-life Costs		0.6	€/h of flight
TOTAL Life Cycle Cost		394.4	€/h of flight
Externalities cost	0.3		
TOTAL Environmental Life Cycle Cost		394.7	€/h of flight

Regarding the UAV unit, 97% of the total LCC is generated during the operation phase (Figure 9). Operation cost is mainly generated for labour costs associated with the processing of the data taken from the flights, since each flight of 16 minutes requires about 1.5 hours to analyse the images and detect where the water leaks are located.

Figure 9. Cost distribution per hour of flight. UAV unit (drone).

5 Economic assessment

A Life Cycle Cost evaluation (LCC) of an asset represents the total cost of its ownership and includes all the costs that will be incurred during the life of the asset to acquire it, operate it, support it and finally dispose it. However, under this approach, the incomes generated with that asset are not taken into account and therefore, either the cash flows generated each year. In order to complement this study, a simplified economic evaluation has been carried out in this deliverable. The objective of this evaluation is to provide an approximate value to assess the profitability of applying the WADI service from the perspective of the company who offers water leaks detection services.

In this light, and within the WP7 activities, Air Marine and Galileo Geosystem performed some estimations about the incomes that they expect to have once the WADI service is ready to be marketed. A data gathering process of all the costs foreseen for the following years was performed and they were compared with the expected incomes, in order to calculate the potential cash flows generated during the next years. From that information, some of the most common economic parameters have been calculated, such as the NPV, IRR or the payback period.

Finally, with the aim of calculating the incomes in prices of 2019, the chosen rate to discount future cash flows is the inflation rate. The predictions made by EUROSTAT [17] indicates that in the next years, inflation will increase in rates around 1.5 %.

The following sections contain the results obtained for both WADI detection systems.

5.1 Manned aircraft. Economic evaluation

In order to perform the economic evaluation of the MAV unit, most of the estimations were made (or validated) by Air Marine. Since the aim of this study is to assess the profitability of the company in charge of offering the water leaks detection service, both the incomes and the costs generated when the MAV WADI service is applied must be taken into account to calculate the profit obtained.

Regarding the income's calculation, it was estimated that the demand of the MAV WADI service could be 400 hours of effective flight every year. In one hour, the MAV unit can monitor 60 km, and the approximate cost for a client who wants to use the MAV WADI service to detected water leaks would be around 30 €/km. In this scenario, the annual incomes would be 720000 €.

On the other hand, the annual increase of the inflation rate has been considered constant and with a value of 1.4 %. To calculate the NPV and the IRR parameters, a 15-year period of time has been considered. Even though the lifetime of the plane, which is the most expensive component of the MAV unit, is about 30 years, it was considered that 15 years is a representative period to consider the profits generated for this service. A detailed analysis of the incomes, costs, profits and cash flows generated each year is collected in Table 14.

The cost of the investment that must be tackled the first year to acquire the complete MAV unit is 782,017€. On the one hand, the aircraft (plane) is the element with the greatest cost (517,620€) but its lifetime is the longest (30 years). On the other hand, other elements such as the IMU cameras or the multispectral camera have a lower investment cost (9,045 € and 24,120 € respectively) but they must be replaced after 6 years. For this reason, in the column of the seventh year in Table 14, a new investment cost appears referring to the required purchase to replace the old cameras.

Taking into account the cash flows calculated for each year, the following economic parameters have been obtained:

- Payback: **3.07 years**
- NPV (15 years): 2,581,458 €
- IRR (15 years): 32 %

The initial investment could be amortized after little more than three years. Besides, the NPV and IRR parameters indicate that the investment incurred to acquire the equipment necessary to offer the MAV WADI service is very profitable. It must be taken into account that for this evaluation, the same number of working hours has been considered for each year. However, once the application of this water leaks detection technique is more consolidated, the demand could annually increase, generating more profits to the company running the service. In addition, and according to the estimations made by Air Marine, after 15 years the plane can still be used to generate more profits until the end of its useful lifetime (30 years).

So, as a preliminary conclusion from this study, the foreseen scenario for the application of the MAV WADI service in the water leaks detection market is quite profitable. However, there are many uncertainty factors, such as the demand or final price of the service that could modify the results obtained in this preliminary economic assessment.

5.2 Unmanned aircraft. Economic evaluation

In the case of the UAV unit, the information required to carry out this economic evaluation was mainly provided by Galileo Geosystem.

Regarding the income's estimation, it was considered that the first year, the WADI service will be used during 600 hours of effective. In the following years, the hours of flight will increase with an annual rate of 2%. Regarding the flight efficiency, it is estimated that in one flight (16min), it would be possible to analyzed 4 hectares. Therefore, in one hour of effective flight, the efficient is 15 ha/h. On the other hand, the price of the service is estimated to be about 30 €/ha. This way, the incomes per hour for the company running the UAV WADI service would be 450 €/h.

Finally, it was considered a 5-year time period to calculate the NPV and IRR parameters. This is the lifetime of the drone structure and after 5 years, some important investment costs should be afforded again to continue offering the WADI service. A detailed summary of the costs incurred, as well as the cash flows obtained each year, can be found in Table 15.

Table 15. Calculation of annual cash flows. UAV unit (5 years)

	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Flight hours [h/year]	0	600	612	624	636	648
Incomes per h of flight [€/h]	0	450	450	450	450	450
Inflation rate, %		1.4%	1.5%	1.6%	1.8%	1.8%
Incomes [€/year]	0	270000€	275400€	280900€	286500€	292200€
Acquisition costs	22312.5	0	0	0	0	0
Drones	2500	0	0	0	0	0
Batteries	2812.5	0	0	2812.5	0	2812.5
Remote control	2000	0	0	0	0	0
Drone others	1000	0	0	0	1000	0
Cameras	4500	0	0	0	0	0
IR camera	3500	0	0	0	0	0
Software	6000	0	0	0	0	0
Maintenance costs	0	2880.0	2937.6	2995.2	3052.8	3110.4
Other maintenance costs (replacements)	0	0	2812.5	0	2812.5	1406.2
Operational costs	0	229508	234098	238688	243278	247868
Labour costs (driving/preparing the drone)	0	56000	57120	58240	59360	60480
Batteries recharging	0	108	110.16	112.32	114.48	116.64
Flying permissions	0	150	153	156	159	162
Visual oversight	0	15750	16065	16380	16695	17010
Data processing costs	0	135000	137700	140400	143100	145800
Other costs	0	22500	22950	23400	23850	24300
End-of-life costs						468
Total costs	22312€	232388€	237036€	241683€	246331€	251447€
Annual cash flows	-22312€	37612€	38364€	39116€	39869€	40153€
Annual current cash flows	-22312€	37093€	37275€	37408€	37453€	37053€

The cost of the initial investment is 22312€. The following years, most of the cost is caused by the operation and maintenance activities. However, the replacement rate of each component has been also taken into account in this evaluation. The set of batteries must be replaced after 2 years and therefore, an investment cost of 2812€ will be afforded in year 3. Besides, other components of the drone will have to be replaced in year 4, causing an additional cost of 1000 years in that year.

As main conclusion from this study, the following economic parameters have been obtained:

- Payback: **0.59 years (7.1 months)**
- NPV (5 years): 163,969 €
- IRR (5 years): 169 %

Looking at these results, the profitability of the investment is clear. The cost of the investment is recovered in less than one year and important profits could be obtained for the company running the flights. However, the profitability of this service will depend on the demand of the service and therefore, the number of effective hours of use of the UAV equipment. If a less optimistic scenario is considered, for example, considering that the machine only is used 200 hours during the first year, the following results are obtained.

- Payback: **1.78 years (21.3 months)**
- NPV (5 years): 39,781 €
- IRR (5 years): 50 %

Under this scenario, the investment is still profitable but much less as in the first scenario. For this reason, performing an accurate market study and the proper business plan is crucial to ensure the success of this technique in the market. In this project, both studies are addressed in WP9.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable aims at performing a Life Cycle Costing assessment of the two water leakage detection techniques developed in the WADI project: MAV and UAV. To do this study, five kind of costs have been taken into consideration: investment, operation, maintenance, end-of-life and externality costs. They all were identified and quantified by using information directly provided from the partners in charge of running the detection service, as well as from information available in scientific publications found in the literature.

Besides the LCC study, a preliminary economic evaluation has been performed in this deliverable. To do this, the incomes that could be obtained for a company running water leakage detection systems have been considered, and taking into account the costs incurred, the expected future cash flows have been estimated to assess the profitability of the service. Finally, some of the most frequent economic parameters have been estimated, such as the NPV and the IRR.

The most relevant conclusions obtaining during this study are collected in the following sections.

6.1 Manned aircraft. Main conclusions

- The LCC of the **MAV** unit is 15,144,000 €. The period of time considered to calculate the costs incurred during the use stage is 30 years, with 400 h/year of effective flights. If the total LCC is linearly distributed between the hours of use, **the LCC per hour of flight is 1,262 €.**
- Most of the LCC is caused by operation costs (82 %). The most significant operation costs are labour costs associated with the time required to process the information taken during the flights. The sum of maintenance and investment costs are responsible for about 17 % of the total costs incurred during the lifetime of the MAV unit. The plane is the component with the greatest cost, but it also the component with the longest lifespan, so its depreciation cost can be more distributed over time. Finally, the end-of-life costs are small in comparison to the remaining costs.

Figure 10. Cost distribution per hour of flight. MAV unit.

- Regarding the economic evaluation performed in this deliverable, and assuming a demand of the service of 400 h/year, the payback of the investment is 3 years, the

NPV is about 2,580,000 € and the IRR is 32 %, being the latest two parameters calculated for a period of 15 years.

6.2 Unmanned aircraft. Main conclusions

- Regarding the **UAV** system, its LCC is 315,600 €. To get this figure, it was estimated a reference lifetime of 5 years, and an effective use of the equipment of 600 h/year. If the total LCC is shared among the total number of hours that is expected to use the equipment, the hourly LCC would be **394.7 €/h of flight**.
- 97 % of the total LCC is caused by operation costs. Within this category, labour costs associated with the flights and with the processing of the images taken by the cameras are the most significant contributors. The costs of the remaining life cycle categories are much lower in comparison.

Life Cycle Cost Distribution UAV

Figure 11. Cost distribution per hour of flight. UAV unit (drone).

- Finally, if an annual demand of 600 hours of effective use of the UAV unit is considered, the initial investment of acquiring the UAV unit could be recovered in 7 months. Under this scenario, the 5-year NPV of the investment would be 164,000 €, and its IRR, 169 %. If a less optimistic scenario is considered (200 hours of UAV service per year), the payback of the investment would be 1.78 years. In both cases, the technology presents high profitability.

7 References

- [1] E. Commission, *Agriculture and water*. .
- [2] S. Renzetti and D. Dupont, *Buried Treasure: The Economics of Leak Detection and Water Loss Prevention in Ontario*, *Environmental Sustainability Research Centre (ESRC) Working Paper Series*, vol. ESRC-2013, p. 14, 2013.
- [3] United Nations-Habitat, *Leakage Control Manual*. 2012.
- [4] M. E. Fontana and D. C. Morais, *Decision model to control water losses in distribution networks*, *Production*, vol. 26, number 4, pp. 688–697, 2016.
- [5] European Commission, *EU Reference document Good Practices on Leakage Management WFD CIS WG PoM*. 2015.
- [6] K. Hill, *Life-cycle Costing*, Paris, France, 2016.
- [7] H. P. Barringer and H. P. Barringer, *A Life Cycle Cost Summary*, in *International Conference of Maintenance Societies (ICOMS – 2003)*, 2003, pp. 1–10.
- [8] M. Pizzol, B. Weidema, M. Brandão, and P. Osset, *Monetary valuation in Life Cycle Assessment: a review*, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 86, pp. 170–179, Jan. 2015.
- [9] European Commission Environment, *Life-cycle costing*, <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>. .
- [10] B. P. Weidema, *Using the budget constraint to monetarise impact assessment results*, *Ecological Economics*, vol. 68, number 6, pp. 1591–1598, Apr. 2009.
- [11] S. O. L. Zijp, *Development of a Life Cycle Cost Model for Conventional and Unconventional Aircraft*, Delft University of Technology, 2014.
- [12] S. Woodford, *Recent Combat Aircraft Life Cycle Costing Developments within DERA*, in *RTO AVT Specialists' Meeting on "Design for Low Cost Operation and Support," 1999*, pp. 0–12.
- [13] X. Zhao, W. J. . Verhagen, and R. Curran, *Aircraft Bi-level Life Cycle Cost Estimation*, in *Transdisciplinary Lifecycle Analysis of Systems: Proceedings of the 22nd ISPE Inc. International Conference on Concurrent Engineering*, 2015, pp. 110–121.
- [14] S. De Bruyn et al., *Environmental Prices Handbook 2017 Methods and numbers for valuation of environmental impacts*, p. 177, 2018.
- [15] L. De Nocker and W. Debacker, *Annex: Monetisation of the MMG method [update 2017]*, p. 65, 2017.
- [16] T. J. Erdman and C. Mitchum, *Acquisition Research Program Sponsored Report Series*, Graduate School of Business & Public Policy, Monterey, 2013.
- [17] EUROSTAT, *Inflation in the euro area*. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Inflation_in_the_euro_area.